

ARBUTIN AND APREMILAST MITIGATE STZ-INDUCED DIABETIC NEPHROPATHY IN RATS VIA INHIBITION OF AGEs, COLLAGEN DEPOSITION, AND INFLAMMATORY PATHWAYS”

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Running Title: Nephroprotective effects of arbutin and apremilast in streptozotocin (STZ)-induced diabetic nephropathy.

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ABSTRACT

Objective: The objective of the study was to evaluate the nephroprotective effects of arbutin and apremilast, against streptozotocin (STZ)-induced diabetic nephropathy in rats.

Methods: Diabetic nephropathy was induced in rats using STZ (55 mg/kg; i.p.). Animals were divided into six groups and treated with arbutin (50 mg/kg; p.o.), apremilast (20 mg/kg; p.o.), and their combination for three weeks. Biochemical parameters (serum glucose, urea, creatinine, uric acid, lipid profile), oxidative stress markers (MDA, GSH, catalase, SOD, NO), inflammatory cytokines (TNF- α , IL-1 β), AGEs, hydroxyproline levels, and histopathology were evaluated. In-silico docking studies were performed to predict the interaction of the compounds with pathological targets.

Results: STZ-induced diabetic rats showed significant metabolic and renal dysfunctions, oxidative stress, and inflammation. Treatment with arbutin and apremilast, both individually and in combination, significantly improved renal function markers, reduced oxidative stress, suppressed TNF- α and IL-1 β levels, and decreased renal fibrosis markers (hydroxyproline and AGEs). Combination therapy exhibited superior protective effects compared to monotherapies. In-silico studies supported strong binding affinities of arbutin and apremilast to hydroxyproline, AGEs, TNF- α and IL-1 β which are key targets involved in diabetic nephropathy pathology. Histopathological analysis confirmed notable restoration of renal architecture.

Conclusion: Arbutin and apremilast exhibited significant nephroprotective effects by ameliorating oxidative stress, inflammation, and fibrosis. Combination therapy offers a promising strategy for the management of diabetic nephropathy, potentially providing a novel adjunct to existing treatments.

Keywords: Arbutin, Apremilast, Diabetic nephropathy, Streptozotocin, Oxidative stress,, Renal protection

INTRODUCTION:

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by elevated blood glucose levels. One of its most severe complications is diabetic nephropathy (DN), which affects approximately 30–40% of diabetic patients and is a leading cause of end-stage renal disease (ESRD) globally, contributing significantly to morbidity and mortality rates^{1,2}. DN is clinically identified by persistent albuminuria and declining glomerular filtration rate (GFR), while histopathologically it is marked by glomerulosclerosis, mesangial expansion, and tubulointerstitial fibrosis³. Although advances in diabetes care have improved glycemic control, current therapeutic strategies for DN, such as renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS) inhibitors like ACE inhibitors and ARBs, offer only partial protection and are often associated with adverse effects⁴. These limitations highlight the urgent need for novel therapeutic agents that target the fundamental pathological mechanisms of DN, including oxidative stress, chronic inflammation,

and fibrosis⁵. In this context, natural compounds with antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties have gained research interest. Arbutin, a naturally occurring glycosylated hydroquinone found in bearberry and blueberry plants, has shown multiple pharmacological benefits. These include antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and anti-glycation activities, and have been reported to reduce oxidative stress, inhibit advanced glycation end products (AGEs), and protect podocytes, ultimately preserving renal function in diabetic models⁶. Apremilast, a phosphodiesterase 4 (PDE4) inhibitor currently approved for psoriasis and psoriatic arthritis, works by elevating intracellular cAMP levels, leading to the suppression of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-1 β . Preclinical data suggests that apremilast may also offer renoprotective effects by targeting inflammation, oxidative stress, and fibrosis, the major drivers of DN progression^{7,8}. This study aims to evaluate the nephroprotective effects of arbutin and apremilast, alone and in combination, in a streptozotocin (STZ)-induced rat model of DN, which closely mimics human disease pathology⁹. A comprehensive analysis of biochemical, oxidative, inflammatory, and histopathological markers was conducted, with losartan included as a standard comparator¹⁰.

The results are expected to provide insights into their mechanisms of action and support the potential of these agents as novel adjunct therapies for diabetic nephropathy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Chemicals

Arbutin (Yucca Enterprises, Mumbai, India); Apremilast (Sun Pharma, India); Losartan (Sun Pharma, India); Streptozotocin (Sigma-Aldrich[®] Lab & Production Materials, Bangalore, India). Arbutin, apremilast and losartan solutions were prepared in distilled water.

Experimental Animals:

Wistar rats (230-250 g) of either sex was used for the study. Animals were procured for seven days and housed in polypropylene cages and maintained under the standard laboratory environmental conditions; temperature 25 \pm 2 $^{\circ}$ C, 12: 12 h L: D cycle and 50 \pm 5% RH with free access to food and water *ad libitum*. Animals were acclimatized to laboratory conditions before the test. All the experimental work carried out during the light period. The study carried out in

harmony with the guidelines given by Committee for the Purpose of Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals (CCSEA), New Delhi (India). The Institutional Animal Ethical Committee of M.V.P.S College of Pharmacy, Nashik approved the protocol of the study (Approval No. IAEC/Oct 2025/08).

Experimental design for STZ induced diabetic nephropathy:

Animals were randomly divided into six groups (n=6). Group I (control): distilled water. Group II Streptozotocin (55 mg/kg; i.p.) was administered once time in fasting condition and observed for 5 weeks. After 5 weeks, treatments were started for next 3 weeks. Group III: Arbutin (50 mg/kg; p.o.), Group IV: Apremilast (20 mg/kg; p.o.), Group V: Losartan (10 mg/kg; p.o.) were administered orally. Losartan used as standard drug. The treatments with arbutin, apremilast, losartan were given for 3 weeks. At the end of experiment, diabetes was confirmed at 72 h after STZ injection by measuring the glucose concentrations of peripheral blood obtained from the tail vein (GlucoOne, Dr Morepen Laboratories, Delhi, India). Diabetes was diagnosed by a sustained glucose concentration >250 mg/dL (>15 mmol/L). The animals were sacrificed using a CO₂ euthanasia chamber on 8th weeks after confirming high blood glucose level. Blood samples and kidney were collected for biochemical analysis. A 24-h urine was collected on the day before the blood sample were taken.

Kidney organ coefficient calculation:

Body weight of rats was weighed after overnight starvation. Then rats were euthanized, and their kidneys were accurately weighed¹¹. The organ coefficient of kidneys was calculated using the following formula:

Kidney organ coefficient = kidney weight (g)/body weight (g).

Computational in-silico docking studies:

To investigate the renoprotective mechanisms of arbutin, apremilast, and losartan, target prediction was performed using Swiss Target Prediction, Super-PRED, and ProTox 3.0 for toxicity. Log P values were obtained by SwissADME. Molecular docking was conducted using SwissDock against key diabetic nephropathy targets such as AGEs, TNF- α , IL-1 β , and hydroxyproline. These targets are implicated in oxidative stress, inflammation, renal fibrosis, and podocyte injury. The study evaluated compound interactions with these proteins to predict potential therapeutic effects.

Biochemical analysis:

After the last administration, rats were individually placed in metabolic cages to collect 24 h urine. Blood samples were collected from the retro orbital venous plexus, in sodium citrate containing tubes and immediately placed on ice. Serum samples were prepared from blood samples by centrifugation (1000g, 10 min, 4 °C). Serums and urine were used for the estimation of serum glucose (GOD/POD method)¹², serum urea (BERTHELOT method), serum uric acid (URICASE Method)¹³, serum creatinine (modified JAFFES method), urine creatinine (modified JAFFES method)¹⁴, total protein (BIURET method)¹⁵, serum cholesterol (CHOD/POD method)¹⁶, serum triglyceride (GOD/POD method)¹⁷ levels were measured using commercial assay kits (Span Diagnostics, India) according to the manufacturer's protocols.

Tissue homogenate preparation

After euthanasia using a CO₂ chamber, kidneys were excised, rinsed with isotonic saline, and weighed. A 10% (w/v) tissue homogenate was prepared in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). The homogenate was centrifuged at 1000 g for 20 min at 4 °C to collect the post-nuclear supernatant for catalase assay. For other antioxidant assays, samples were further centrifuged at 12,000 g for 60 min at 4 °C. Biochemical analyses were performed using a Spectrostar Nano reader (BMG Labtech, Germany)¹⁸.

Antioxidant evaluation:**Estimation of catalase activity (CAT):**

Catalase activity was estimated using the Luck (1971) method by measuring the decrease in H₂O₂ absorbance at 240 nm. The reaction mixture contained 3 ml of 0.01 M H₂O₂-phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) and 0.05 ml of 10% tissue homogenate. Absorbance change was recorded for 1 minute, and activity was calculated using an extinction coefficient of 0.071 mM⁻¹cm⁻¹¹⁹.

Estimation of superoxide dismutase level (SOD):

SOD activity was determined using the Kono method, which measures the inhibition of nitroblue tetrazolium (NBT) reduction at 560 nm. The reaction was initiated with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in the presence of EDTA, NBT, Triton X-100, and tissue homogenate. Results were expressed as the percentage inhibition of NBT reduction²⁰.

Estimation of malondialdehyde (Lipid peroxidation assay- LPO):

Lipid peroxidation was estimated using the Wills (1966) method by measuring malondialdehyde (MDA) levels by its reaction with thiobarbituric acid (TBA) at 532 nm. The reaction mixture was heated at 95 °C, followed by extraction with butanol-pyridine and centrifugation. Absorbance of the organic layer was recorded, and MDA concentration was calculated using an extinction coefficient of $1.56 \times 10^5 \text{ M}^{-1}\text{cm}^{-1}$ ²¹.

Estimation of reduced glutathione level (GSH):

Reduced glutathione (GSH) in the brain was measured using Ellman's method. Brain homogenate was precipitated with 4% sulphosalicylic acid and centrifuged. The supernatant was mixed with DTNB in phosphate buffer (pH 8.0), producing a yellow color measured at 412 nm. Results were expressed as μM of GSH per milligram of protein²².

Estimation of nitric oxide (NO):

Sodium nitroprusside (5 mM, 0.1 ml) in 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7) was incubated with the test sample at room temperature for 30 minutes. After incubation, 0.5 ml of the mixture was reacted with 0.5 ml of Griess reagent, and absorbance was measured at 543 nm. Nitrite concentration was calculated from a sodium nitrite standard curve and expressed as micromoles of nitrite per milliliter of homogenate²³.

Estimation of hydroxyproline assay:

The hydroxyproline content in kidney tissues was measured to assess the quantification of collagen. Hydroxyproline has been widely used as an indicator of both the presence and the metabolism of collagen. Chopped kidney tissues were transferred into a 6M hydrochloric-acid, sealed and kept in an oven overnight at 110°C. The solution was evaporated to eliminate excess acid and hydrolyzed samples were dissolved in 1ml of PBS and added 1 ml of Chloramine T reagent to it. The sample was mixed well for 20 min, after mixing 1 ml of DMAB reagent was added and the mixture was incubated at 60°C. The absorbance of samples was measured at 550 nm²⁴.

Estimation of advanced glycation end product (AGEs):

Kidney AGEs levels were estimated using the method of Sensi et al. (1996). Kidney tissue was homogenized in 0.25 M sucrose and centrifuged at 900 g, 5°C. The pellet was washed twice with sucrose, and combined supernatants were treated with trichloroacetic acid to precipitate proteins. After centrifugation, the protein pellet was washed with methanol to remove lipids, then washed with 10% cold TCA. The insoluble protein was solubilized in 1 M NaOH, and protein concentration was determined by absorbance at 280 nm using a BSA standard curve²⁵.

Estimation of TNF- α and IL-1 β levels in kidney: Pro-inflammatory markers

The quantification of levels of TNF- α and IL-1 β in kidney were performed by ELISA kit (Krishgen Biosystems, USA) as per instructions of the manufacturer using a microplate reader. The concentrations of TNF- α and IL-1 β were calculated from standard curves^{26,27}.

Histopathological analysis:

The rat kidneys were examined for histopathological evaluation. The kidneys were removed and immediately fixed in 10% buffered formalin. The kidney, which had been alcohol-dehydrated and embedded in paraffin, was sectioned to reveal the glomerular volume. Using a microtome, five-micrometer thick serial histological slices were cut from paraffin blocks and stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E). Digital microscope (Olympus, Japan), was used to analyse the sections under a light microscope while taking photomicrographs²⁸.

Statistical analysis:

All results were represented as mean \pm S.E.M. Graph Pad Prism 9.5.1 software was used to evaluate all the group data using one-way analysis of variance and Dunnett's test. (GraphPad[®], San Diego, CA, USA).

RESULTS:**In-silico docking studies**

Theoretical docking was performed to evaluate the nephroprotective potential of arbutin and apremilast against key diabetic nephropathy mediators, including AGEs, hydroxyproline, TNF- α , and IL-1 β , the targets associated with oxidative stress, inflammation, and fibrosis. Arbutin exhibited strong binding affinities to AGE-related receptors and inflammatory cytokines, supporting its antioxidant and anti-glycation effects. Apremilast showed interaction with TNF- α ,

IL-1 β , NF- κ B, and TGF- β 1, indicating its potential to suppress inflammation and fibrosis. Binding affinity values for both agents were comparable to losartan, reinforcing their role as promising nephroprotective candidates.

Table 1: Calculated binding affinities for different targets.

Targets	PDB ID	Calculated affinity of drugs (Kcal/mol)		
		Arbutin (A)	Apremilast (B)	Losartan (C)
AGEs	2e5e	-5.9	-6.8	-6.9
Hydroxyproline	3kfd	-6.5	-7.1	-8.5
TNF- α	1TNF	-7.9	-6.2	-5.9
IL-1 β	1LT β	-6.5	-7.0	-8.0

Figure 1(A): Binding with AGEs by arbutin, apremilast and losartan respectively

Figure 1(B): Binding with hydroxyproline by arbutin, apremilast and losartan respectively

Figure 1(C): Binding with TNF- α by arbutin, apremilast and losartan respectively

Figure 1(D): Binding with IL-1 β by arbutin, apremilast and losartan respectively

The data of toxicity prediction of Software (ProTox 3.0) indicated LD₅₀ of arbutin is 2500 mg/kg (Oral), toxicity class-5 and LD₅₀ of apremilast is 12000 mg/kg (Oral), toxicity class-6.

SwissADME software showed Log p value of arbutin 1.64 (lipophilic) and apremilast 3.10 (moderately lipophilic).

Effect of arbutin and apremilast on body weight

STZ-induced rats showed a significant ($p < 0.0001$) reduction in body weight. Treatment with arbutin, apremilast their combination, and losartan significantly ($p < 0.01$ to $p < 0.001$) restored body weight compared to the STZ group (Table 2).

Effect of arbutin and apremilast on kidney weight

STZ-induced rats indicated a significant ($p < 0.0001$) decrease in kidney weight. Treatment with arbutin, apremilast their combination, and losartan significantly ($p < 0.01$ to $p < 0.001$) increased

kidney weight compared to the STZ group (Table 2).

Effect of arbutin and apremilast on renal indices

STZ-induced rats exhibited a significant ($p < 0.0001$) decrease in renal index. Arbutin, apremilast their combination and losartan significantly ($p < 0.01$ to $p < 0.001$) improved the renal index compared to the STZ group (Table 2).

Table 2: Effect of arbutin and apremilast on body weight, kidney weight and renal indices

Treatments	Body weight	Kidney weight	Renal indices
Control	243 ± 2.5	2.1 ± 0.032	0.93 ± 0.013
Streptozotocin (55 mg/kg; i.p.)	149 ± 2.7 ^{###}	1.4 ± 0.02 ^{###}	0.53 ± 0.013 ^{###}
Arbutin (50 mg/kg; p.o.)	191 ± 1.7 ^{***}	1.5 ± 0.013 ^{***}	0.62 ± 0.0075 ^{***}
Apremilast (20 mg/kg; p.o.)	200 ± 2.5 ^{***}	1.6 ± 0.012 ^{***}	0.58 ± 0.016 [*]
Arbutin (50 mg/kg; p.o.) + Apremilast (20 mg/kg; p.o.)	221 ± 1.5 ^{***}	1.7 ± 0.014 ^{***}	0.68 ± 0.0097 ^{***}
Losartan (10 mg/kg; p.o.)	231 ± 1.7 ^{***}	1.8 ± 0.014 ^{***}	0.77 ± 0.0089 ^{***}

Values were expressed as mean ± S.E.M. (n = 6) in each group. #Group II compared to Group I. *Groups III, IV, V and VI are compared to Group II. (One-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's test.). ^{ns}-Non significant, #, * $p < 0.05$, ##, * $p < 0.01$, and ###, *** $p < 0.001$.

Effect of arbutin and apremilast on serum glucose

STZ-induced group showed a significant ($p < 0.0001$) increase in serum glucose as compared to the control group. Arbutin (50 mg/kg p.o.) and apremilast (10 mg/kg p.o.) revealed a significant ($p < 0.01$) decrease in serum glucose. The combination of arbutin and apremilast ($p < 0.001$) also indicated a significant decrease in serum glucose as compared to the STZ-induced group. Losartan, a standard drug, showed a significant ($p < 0.001$) decrease in serum glucose as compared to the STZ group (Table 3).

Effect of arbutin and apremilast on serum urea, uric acid, and creatinine levels

The findings of STZ-induced group indicated a significant ($p < 0.0001$) increase in serum urea, uric acid and creatinine as compared to the control group. Arbutin (50 mg/kg p.o.) and apremilast (10 mg/kg p.o.) demonstrated a significant ($p < 0.01$) decrease in serum urea, uric acid and creatinine levels. The combination of arbutin and apremilast ($p < 0.001$) also indicated a significant decrease in serum urea, uric acid and creatinine concentrations as compared to the

STZ-induced group. Similar results found with losartan ($p < 0.001$) (Table 3).

Effect of arbutin and apremilast on creatinine clearance

Treatment with STZ illustrated a significant ($p < 0.0001$) decrease in creatinine clearance as compared to the control group. Arbutin (50 mg/kg p.o.) and apremilast (10 mg/kg p.o.) indicated a significantly ($p < 0.01$) increase in creatinine clearance. The combination of arbutin and apremilast ($p < 0.001$) also showed greater significant increase in urine creatinine as compared to the STZ-induced group. Losartan, also showed a significant ($p < 0.001$) increase in creatinine clearance (Table 3).

Effect of arbutin and apremilast on total protein in urine

STZ-induced group showed a significant ($p < 0.0001$) increase in total protein as compared to the control group. Arbutin (50 mg/kg p.o.) and apremilast (10 mg/kg p.o.) revealed a significant ($p < 0.01$) decrease in total protein. The combination of arbutin and apremilast ($p < 0.001$) also showed a significant decrease in total protein as compared to the STZ-induced group. Losartan showed a significant ($p < 0.001$) decrease in total protein as compared to the STZ group (Table 3).

Effect of arbutin and apremilast on serum cholesterol and triglyceride levels

STZ-induced group showed a significant ($p < 0.0001$) increase in serum cholesterol and triglyceride levels as compared to the control group. Arbutin (50 mg/kg p.o.) and apremilast (10 mg/kg p.o.) showed a significant ($p < 0.01$) decrease in serum cholesterol and triglyceride levels. The combination of arbutin and apremilast ($p < 0.001$) also showed a significant decrease in serum cholesterol and triglyceride levels as compared to the STZ-induced group. Losartan, a standard drug, showed a significant ($p < 0.001$) decrease in serum cholesterol and triglyceride as compared to the STZ group (Table 3).

Table 3: Effect of arbutin and apremilast on biochemical parameters

Treatments	Serum glucose (mg/dl)	Serum urea (g/litre)	Serum uric acid (mg/dl)	Serum creatinine (mg/dl)	Creatinine clearance (mL/min)	Total protein (g/dl)	Serum cholesterol (mg/dl)	Serum triglyceride (mg/dl)
Control	96.6 ± 2.205	39 ± 0.59	4 ± 0.18	0.63 ± 0.0114	1.4 ± 0.0071	3.8 ± 0.077	10 ± 3.2	122 ± 3.6

Streptozotocin (55 mg/kg, i.p.)	351.2 ± 2.577 [#]	69 ± 0.58 [#]	10 ± 0.17 [#]	1.522 ± 0.01114 ^{###}	0.53 ± 0.014 ^{###}	6.8 ± 0.077 ^{###}	387 ± 2.1 ^{###}	264 ± 3.5 ^{###}
Arbutin (50 mg/kg, p.o.)	161.2 ± 2.577 ^{***}	56 ± 0.59 ^{***}	7 ± 0.19 ^{***}	1.24 ± 0.01703 ^{***}	0.75 ± 0.0093 ^{***}	5.4 ± 0.049 ^{***}	257 ± 2.1 ^{***}	185 ± 2 ^{***}
Apremilast (20 mg/kg, p.o.)	178.2 ± 5.142 ^{***}	54 ± 0.59 ^{***}	8.3 ± 0.12 ^{***}	1.22 ± 0.008367 ^{***}	0.7 ± 0.0071 ^{***}	5.8 ± 0.077 ^{***}	237 ± 2.1 ^{***}	191 ± 1.7 ^{***}
Arbutin (50 mg/kg, p.o.) + Apremilast (20 mg/kg, p.o.)	144.2 ± 1.497 ^{***}	52 ± 0.58 ^{***}	6.8 ± 0.16 ^{***}	1.134 ± 0.01288 ^{***}	0.97 ± 0.0075 ^{***}	5.2 ± 0.055 ^{***}	277 ± 2.1 ^{***}	221 ± 2.3 ^{***}
Losartan (10 mg/kg, p.o.)	122.2 ± 2.01 ^{***}	49 ± 0.41 ^{***}	5.8 ± 0.16 ^{***}	0.922 ± 0.008602 ^{***}	1.1 ± 0.011 ^{***}	4.8 ± 0.077 ^{***}	290 ± 3.3 ^{***}	236 ± 2.4 ^{***}

Values were expressed as mean ± S.E.M. (n = 6) in each group. [#]Group II compared to Group I.

*Groups III, IV, V and VI are compared to Group II. (One-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's test.). ^{ns}-Non significant, [#], * p < 0.05, ^{##}, * p < 0.01, and ^{###}, ^{***} p < 0.001.

Effect of arbutin and apremilast on catalase (CAT), superoxide dismutase (SOD) and reduced glutathione level (GSH) levels

STZ-induced group showed a significant (p<0.0001) decrease in catalase, superoxide dismutase and reduced glutathione levels as compared to the control group. Arbutin (50 mg/kg p.o.) and apremilast (10 mg/kg p.o.) showed a significant (p<0.01) increase in catalase, superoxide dismutase and reduced glutathione levels. The combination of arbutin and apremilast (p<0.001) also showed a greater significant increase in catalase, superoxide dismutase and reduced glutathione levels as compared to the STZ-induced group. Losartan showed a significant (p<0.001) increase in catalase, superoxide dismutase and reduced glutathione levels as compared to the STZ group (Table 4).

Effect of arbutin and apremilast on lipid peroxidation (LPO) and nitric oxide (NO) levels

STZ-induced group showed a significant ($p < 0.0001$) increase in lipid peroxidation and nitric oxide levels as compared to the control group. Arbutin (50 mg/kg p.o.) and apremilast (10 mg/kg p.o.) showed a significant ($p < 0.01$) decrease in lipid peroxidation and nitric oxide levels. The combination of arbutin and apremilast ($p < 0.001$) also showed a significant decrease in lipid peroxidation and nitric oxide levels as compared to the STZ-induced group. Losartan also decreased ($p < 0.001$) lipid peroxidation and nitric oxide levels as compared to the STZ group (Table 4).

Table 4: Effect of arbutin and apremilast on oxidative parameters

Treatments	CAT (μ moles of H_2O_2 decomposed/ mg protein/min)	SOD (% inhibition of reduction of NBT)	GSH (μ moles of GSH/mg proteins)	LPO (n moles of MDA/mg proteins)	NO (μ moles of Nitrite/ mg of proteins)
Control	8.5 \pm 0.057	89 \pm 0.68	7.8 \pm 0.043	1.4 \pm 0.093	29 \pm 0.39
Streptozotocin (55 mg/kg, i.p.)	2.7 \pm 0.071 ^{###}	28 \pm 0.58 ^{###}	1.8 \pm 0.044 ^{###}	6.6 \pm 0.058 ^{###}	52 \pm 0.4 ^{###}
Arbutin (50 mg/kg, p.o.)	4.3 \pm 0.062 ^{***}	59 \pm 0.59 ^{***}	4.3 \pm 0.063 ^{***}	4.3 \pm 0.059 ^{***}	49 \pm 0.39 ^{***}
Apremilast (20 mg/kg, p.o.)	5.6 \pm 0.067 ^{***}	66 \pm 0.64 ^{***}	4.7 \pm 0.053 ^{***}	3.3 \pm 0.059 ^{***}	43 \pm 0.42 ^{***}
Arbutin (50 mg/kg, p.o.) +Apremilas(20mg/kg,p.o)	6.3 \pm 0.056 ^{***}	82 \pm 0.56 ^{***}	6.5 \pm 0.043 ^{***}	2.1 \pm 0.042 ^{***}	36 \pm 0.42 ^{***}
Losartan (10 mg/kg; p.o.)	7.8 \pm 0.053 ^{***}	87 \pm 0.4 ^{***}	7.2 \pm 0.074 ^{***}	1.8 \pm 0.042 ^{***}	32 \pm 0.4 ^{***}

Values were expressed as mean \pm S.E.M. (n = 6) in each group. #Group II compared to Group I. *Groups III, IV, V and VI are compared to Group II. (One-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's test.). ^{ns}-Non significant, #, * p < 0.05, ##, * p < 0.01, and ###, *** p < 0.001.

Effect of arbutin and apremilast on hydroxyproline level

STZ-induced group showed a significant (p<0.0001) increase in hydroxyproline level as compared to the control group, indicating collagen deposition and fibrosis. Arbutin (50 mg/kg p.o.) and apremilast (10 mg/kg p.o.) showed a significant (p<0.01) decrease in hydroxyproline level, thus decrease in collagen deposition and, consequently, a reduction in the severity of fibrosis. The combination of arbutin and apremilast (p<0.001) also showed a significant decrease in hydroxyproline level as compared to the STZ-induced group. Losartan, a standard drug, showed a significant (p<0.001) decrease in hydroxyproline level as compared to the STZ group (Fig 2).

Figure 2: Effect of arbutin and apremilast on hydroxyproline level in STZ-induced diabetic nephropathy in rats.

Each column represents mean \pm S.E.M. (n = 6) in each group. #Group II compared to Group I. *Groups III, IV, V and VI are compared to Group II. (One-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's test.). ^{ns}-Non significant, #, * p < 0.05, ##, * p < 0.01, and ###, *** p < 0.001.

Effect of arbutin and apremilast on advanced glycation end product (AGEs) level

STZ-induced group showed a significant (p<0.0001) increase in advanced glycation end product level as compared to the control group, suggesting diabetic nephropathy. Arbutin (50 mg/kg p.o.) and apremilast (10 mg/kg p.o.) showed a significant (p<0.01) decrease in advanced glycation end

product level. The combination of arbutin and apremilast ($p < 0.001$) also showed a significant decrease in advanced glycation end product level as compared to the STZ-induced group. Losartan, a standard drug, showed a significant ($p < 0.001$) decrease in advanced glycation end product level as compared to the STZ group (Fig 3).

Figure 3: Effect of arbutin and apremilast on advanced glycation end (AGEs) product level in STZ induced diabetic nephropathy in rats.

Each column represents mean \pm S.E.M. ($n = 6$) in each group. #Group II compared to Group I. *Groups III, IV, V and VI are compared to Group II. (One-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's test.). ns-Non significant, #, * $p < 0.05$, ##, * $p < 0.01$, and ###, *** $p < 0.001$.

Effect of arbutin and apremilast on pro-inflammatory markers (TNF- α and IL-1 β levels)

STZ-induced group showed a significant ($p < 0.0001$) increase in TNF- α and IL-1 β levels as compared to the control group. Arbutin (50 mg/kg p.o.) and apremilast (10 mg/kg p.o.) showed a significant ($p < 0.01$) decrease in TNF- α and IL-1 β levels. The combination of arbutin and apremilast ($p < 0.001$) also showed a significant decrease in TNF- α and IL-1 β levels as compared to the STZ-induced group. Losartan showed a significant ($p < 0.001$) decrease in TNF- α and IL-1 β levels as compared to the STZ group (Fig 4a and 4b).

Figure 4: Effect of arbutin and apremilast on (a) TNF- α , (b) IL-1 β levels in STZ induced diabetic nephropathy in rats.

Histopathological analysis

Figure 5: Histopathological changes of glomerular region of rat's kidney.

Histopathological analysis of the rat kidney (glomerular region) revealed normal glomerular architecture in control animals, with intact Bowman's capsules and normal mesangial structure. Animals treated with STZ exhibited severe glomerular damage, including mesangial expansion, glomerular hypertrophy, basement membrane thickening, and signs of sclerosis, indicating diabetic nephropathy-induced injury. Treatment with arbutin (50 mg/kg p.o.) improved glomerular morphology by reducing mesangial expansion and preventing podocyte damage, attributed to its antioxidant and anti-glycation effects. Apremilast (20 mg/kg p.o.) also showed renal protective effects by attenuating inflammatory infiltration and glomerular fibrosis through cytokine modulation. The combination of arbutin and apremilast resulted in significant improvement in glomerular architecture, reducing both inflammatory and fibrotic changes more effectively than either drug alone. Losartan (10 mg/kg p.o.) preserved glomerular structure and reduced diabetic injury, confirming its protective role in diabetic nephropathy.

DISCUSSION

The present study investigates the nephroprotective potential of arbutin and apremilast in STZ-induced diabetic nephropathy (DN) in rats. STZ administration induces persistent hyperglycemia and triggers significant alterations in renal function, oxidative stress, inflammatory markers, fibrosis, and kidney histology. The results of this study demonstrate that both arbutin and apremilast, especially in combination, significantly mitigate these pathological changes.

STZ-treated rats exhibit a marked reduction in body weight, kidney weight, and renal index, reflecting systemic catabolic effects and renal atrophy^{5,29}. Arbutin and apremilast individually

restore these parameters, and their combination produces greater improvement, suggesting metabolic stabilization and organ preservation. These effects align with previous studies reporting protective actions of antioxidants and anti-inflammatory agents in DN^{6,9}.

Significant elevation in serum glucose levels in diabetic rats confirms sustained hyperglycemia, a hallmark of DN^{1,4}. Treatment with arbutin and apremilast reduces serum glucose levels, with the combination showing enhanced glycemic control. Arbutin may achieve this by reducing oxidative stress and inhibiting glycation⁶, while apremilast acts via PDE4 inhibition and cAMP elevation to suppress inflammation-induced insulin resistance⁷.

STZ-induced nephropathy results in increased serum urea, uric acid, creatinine, and urinary protein, along with decreased creatinine clearance, indicating impaired glomerular filtration and renal dysfunction^{2,25}. All these biochemical markers are significantly reversed by arbutin and apremilast, with combination therapy demonstrating greater efficacy. These outcomes are comparable to those observed with losartan, a standard renoprotective agent¹⁰.

Diabetic rats also show elevated serum cholesterol and triglycerides, indicative of dyslipidemia. Treatment with both agents restores lipid levels, possibly by reducing oxidative stress and modulating lipid metabolism^{10,28}. This lipid-lowering effect helps prevent further renal vascular injury associated with diabetic complications.

Oxidative stress is a central mechanism in DN, characterized by increased lipid peroxidation (LPO) and nitric oxide (NO), and decreased levels of antioxidant enzymes such as catalase (CAT), superoxide dismutase (SOD), and glutathione (GSH)^{4,18,21}. Arbutin and apremilast individually restore antioxidant enzyme activity and reduce LPO and NO levels. Their combination enhances the antioxidant defense system more effectively, protecting against free radical-induced damage^{6,8,30}.

Fibrotic remodeling is evidenced by elevated hydroxyproline levels, indicating increased collagen deposition and fibrosis in diabetic kidneys. Arbutin and apremilast significantly reduce hydroxyproline content, thereby attenuating fibrosis. The effect is most prominent with combination therapy, likely due to the suppression of TGF- β 1 signaling and oxidative stress^{8,28,31}.

The accumulation of advanced glycation end products (AGEs) is another critical contributor to DN progression. Diabetic kidneys exhibit significantly increased AGEs, which promote inflammation, fibrosis, and oxidative stress²⁵. Arbutin, known for its anti-glycation properties, and apremilast, by reducing oxidative and inflammatory burden, effectively reduce AGE accumulation. The combination group shows superior reduction, further supporting their complementary mechanisms^{6,25}.

The inflammatory cascade in DN involves elevated levels of TNF- α and IL-1 β , which contribute to glomerular and tubular injury. Both arbutin and apremilast significantly suppress these cytokines, and their combination exhibits enhanced anti-inflammatory action. Apremilast achieves this through PDE4 inhibition and downregulation of NF- κ B activity, while arbutin reduces oxidative triggers that amplify cytokine release^{7,26,27,29}.

Histological evaluation further supports the biochemical results. Diabetic rats show severe glomerular hypertrophy, mesangial expansion, basement membrane thickening, and tubular atrophy, all characteristic of advanced DN^{1,3}. Treated groups, especially those receiving combination therapy, show preservation of normal kidney architecture, with reduced fibrosis and inflammation. These structural improvements correlate well with the observed functional recovery and align with findings from other renoprotective interventions like losartan¹⁰.

In addition, in-silico docking studies confirm the potential molecular targets of arbutin and apremilast. Both compounds show strong binding affinities with key DN mediators, including AGEs, hydroxyproline, TNF- α , and IL-1 β . Their binding energies are comparable to those of losartan, suggesting a multi-targeted mode of action. Toxicity profiling also confirms their safety at therapeutic doses, further supporting their pharmacological suitability.

In conclusion, this study demonstrates that arbutin and apremilast significantly reverse metabolic, biochemical, oxidative, inflammatory, and fibrotic changes in STZ-induced diabetic nephropathy. Their combination therapy provides superior nephroprotection through synergistic mechanisms involving anti-hyperglycemic, antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-glycation, and anti-fibrotic pathways. These findings highlight their potential as promising adjunct or alternative therapeutic strategies for the management of diabetic nephropathy.

CONCLUSION

The present study demonstrates that both arbutin and apremilast exhibited significant nephroprotective effects in STZ-induced diabetic nephropathy through distinct yet complementary mechanisms. Arbutin effectively reduced hyperglycemia, improved renal function, restored antioxidant defenses, and attenuated glycation and fibrotic markers due to its potent antioxidant and anti-glycation properties. Apremilast, a PDE4 inhibitor, conferred protection by suppressing pro-inflammatory cytokines, reducing oxidative stress, and improving renal histopathology, likely through NF- κ B and TGF- β 1 pathway modulation.

Most notably, the combination of arbutin and apremilast provided superior protection compared to monotherapy or the standard reference drug, losartan. This combination led to more pronounced improvements in biochemical markers, oxidative stress parameters, inflammation, and histological restoration, indicating a synergistic and multi-targeted therapeutic effect.

Taken together, these findings suggest that arbutin and apremilast particularly in combination may serve as promising therapeutic candidates for the management of diabetic nephropathy. Their ability to target multiple pathological pathways highlights their potential for further development as adjunct or alternative strategies to current treatment options.

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